
THE BRITISH COLONIAL ADMINISTRATION IN OGBOMOSOLAND 1900-1960

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Abstract

The paper examines the British administrative system in colonial Ogbomoso. It identifies and analyses how Ogbomoso became a safe-haven for traditional rulers and their subjects during the Yoruba civil wars of 19th century. The inception of British in Yorubaland in 1893 created a new epoch in administrative system among Yoruba race and Ogbomoso inclusive. The then Bale Ogbomoso was saddled with responsibility of administrative and judicial matter as well as political head of the town with the support of his llu chiefs for utmost performance. This work therefore looks at the Native Local Authority system in colonial Ogbomoso and its effects on post-colonial socio-political system. Its methodology consists of archival and supplemented with a few existing written works on Ogbomoso history. The paper gave a clear picture of colonial administrative system in the town. It equally identified the role played by Soun of Ogbomoso in the colonial administration. The paper recommended that current local government system should be effectively utilized for good governance in Nigeria.

Keyword: Administration, Traditional, Chieftaincy, Pre-colonial, Ogbomoso.

Introduction

The hitherto existing indigenous of administration in Yorubaland in general and Ogbomoso in particular was made to have their relevance in the context of colonial rule itself received an impetus in the aftermath of the famous Berlin Conference of 1884/1885 championed by German chancellor Otto Von Bismark. Though the local administration in pre-colonial Ogbomoso met the needs of the people, the coming of foreign rule led to its discredit by the Europeans. Therefore, the traditional system of administration was modified to suit the imperial passion of the British lords.

The colonial period remained an important epoch in the socio-political evolution of Ogbomoso. The administration of Nigeria was based on a system devised by Lord Lugard where the British ruled through the existing political institution rather than establishing a wholly new form of administration at the local level.

Given the example of Ogbomoso one observes that tradition institution were employed to enforce law and order despite the fact that were series of revolts. The traditional rulers were more relevant and empowered in the colonial cabinet to perform legislative, executive and judicial administrative functions of town and villages within Oyo province and Ogbomoso District in particular.

The 1893 treaty that ended the Yoruba civil wars recognized the right of Ibadan to administer a vast area which included Ogbomoso [Dickson 1935 NAI]; although the Alaafin was recognized as the head of Yoruba land. But by 1917, the District officer in Ibadan directed all the head of large towns and villages as the subordinate Native Authority of their towns to administer them on behalf of British colonial Officers. From this on the Bale of Ogbomoso was empowered to administer the town with the support of his Ilu chiefs for the collection of taxes and implementation could still be found in the present day Ogbomoso local administration.

The brief history of Ogbomoso

The earliest written records on Ogbomoso was carried out by explorers and missionaries, who provided insight to the ancestral history of the town [Atanda 1973], But this early writers from 1855 wrote from their own cultural and sociological background for both foreign and local audience. Ogbomoso, as it is today, falls within the territory of Oyo state. It is the second largest city in the state. Located between Ilorin and Oyo, the city which is about equidistance between Ilorin and Oyo is built on plan level land. Its ambiguous feature of savanna grassland and thick forest bush contributed to the development of agriculture in the town in general. After many years since it was founded, Ogbomoso is still largely an agrarian town [Edo 2011].

There are two related version of the historical origin and evolution of Ogbomoso. The first version informed that the place that became known as Ogbomoso from the 18th century could not be described as a single political entity with recognized or recognizable authority of a ruling house on others. The place could be described as a tiny village in rough spherical shape of hurting and farming camps of about five dwellers. The second version traced the history of the town to the second half of the 18th century. There is a considerable agreement on historical tradition which ascribes the founding of Ogbomoso to five personalities who came to settle down in the area from different directions.

The first settler on the site of Ogbomoso was a Nupe hunter called Aale, who killed an elephant and made his camp at the place still known as Okeelerin. His family became the Bale Okeelerin in chieftaincy family.

The second was Ohunsile an Awori prince from Ota in present day Ogun State. It is descendants are traced to the present chieftaincy family of BaleIjeru. Orisatolu a Bariba from Parakou (Dahomey) where he killed a man with medicine and he had to flee on arrival in his camp he planted vegetable known as “Isapa” and was called Baba Onisapa. From there his camp or quarter was known as Isapa while Akande’s preceded the family of Soun to the area of Ogbomoso. His family retained the title of Akande in Isale Afon ward before the family became extinct. Ogunlola the fifth settler and co-founder gave rise to the Soun ruling dynasty. He was reported to have come from Ibariba land. (Dickson,1938). Upon his arrival, he moved southward where he met four other hunters: Aale, Ohunsile, Orisatolu and Akande. The prowess of Ogunlola soon made him primus inter pares and it was only a matter of time before he brought others under his control. From then, the town began to grow stronger and stronger up to the early part of the 19th century when civil war ravaged the entire Yoruba land.

The endemic warfare in the Yorubaland in the 19th century left trails of political chaos and large scale destruction of lives, property and massive population dislocation leading to the proliferation of refugees all over Yorubaland to Ogbomoso’s advantage. Refugees fled their homes in different forms as individuals, corporate families or town with their traditional institution such as Obas, chiefs and ancestral gods and goddess into host towns and village. These people were influenced in their choice of hosts by the concern for safe geographical location, political and cultural affiliation as well as the capacity of their hosts to afford their protection. The last factor influenced migration to Ogbomoso [Ogbomoso, 1998].

However, the various groups of refugees were integrated by their hosts. Each refugee settlement became a quarter or ward of the host town. The most senior chief of refugee town thus became a quarter chief in Ogbomoso. For instance the Olugbon of igbon, Aresa of ireda, Onpetu of ijeru, Onikoyi of ikoyi to mention few retained their titles by their host, soun. The beaded Obas such as Onpetu, Aresa, Olugbon had to subject themselves to the Baale of Ogbomoso’s authority. The colonial administrator followed what was on ground when they settled down in the town NAL.

Pre-colonial Administration in Ogbomoso

The early history of Ogbomoso revolves around the issue of migration. With the passage of time Soun brought all the four settlers [Aale of Oke-Elerin, Ohunsile of Ijeru quarters, Orisatolu of Isapa and Akandie quarters]under his control and in the process established his dynasty as the ruling house in Ogbomoso but acknowledged the Alaafin as his immediate superior. The founding of the town is officially dated to soun’s settlement in the area. The town’s internal administration arrogated many powers to the Baale [as the ruler of Ogbomoso was called until 1952 when the title was changed to soun] [Oyerinde, 1937]. All the first settlers in Ogbomoso are now acknowledged by the appellation given to some office holders in the town. Successive Baale have pursued this policy possibly out of the confusion that the descendants of these settlers may later lay traditional claims to the headship of their quarters within the town.

In the early days of settlement, Soun Ogunlola was known as a quarrelsome person one day, he quarrelled with one of his wife’s customers who refused to pay for the service she rendered [sale of millet beer] . A struggle ensued and he eventually killed the customer who

was known as Baba Ijesa as a result this act he was sent to Alaafin for punishment where he was imprisoned. While awaiting trial he pleaded with the Alaafin and the Oyomesi to grant him permission to fight a marauder who was troubling and killing the citizen of Oyo Empire in a mysterious way. He was permitted; Soun to the consternation of everyone killed the man Elemoso [Oyerinde, 1934]. In recognition of his bravery he was granted state pardon and given jurisdiction over his immediate area of settlement and was referred to as Soun Ogbori Elemoso. This was later shortened to Ogbomoso [Oyerinde 1934]. He founded the institution of kingship in the town and his first name Soun became the title of subsequent kings of Ogbomoso.

Soun was and is still the head of the traditional administration in Ogbomoso. Law making was the duty of the Soun and the member of his council consisted of the most senior chiefs in Ogbomoso. These are Areago, Jagun, Ikolaba, Baara, Abese, Iyalode and Balogun. Each of these chiefs has specific roles to perform in the administration of the town. For example, Jagun was the captain of the army as well as the market supervisor and head of police. The Are-ago was the head of Soun's bodyguard. Ikolaba was the chamberlain, while Baara was the head of farmers NAL.

Furthermore in the initial period after the founding of the town, the Baale maintained a strict overall administrative control by retaining the power to appoint and depose at will the Ilu chiefs who constituted the policy making council. As a reflection of its military origin the position of the Ilu chiefs was open to all aspirants among the later arrivals in the town who demonstrated martial valor. Life in the town became more settled towards the end of the 18th century. His administrative acumen paved way for absolute control of the town and its suburb.

At least on two occasions, the wide administrative powers enjoyed by the bale were curtailed by the Alaafin. Two Baale were removed from office by the Alaafin following allegations made by the Ilu chiefs against them that they violated some tradition of the town (Agiri 1966). These instances are cherished by the Ilu chiefs and people for vindicating and safeguarding their constitutional right against the arbitrariness of bale for Ogbomoso. The power relation between Baale and Ilu chiefs underwent important and rapid changes during the 19th century. Beginning with Toyeye rulership in the town (1790-1825) he succeeded Afonja of Ilorin as the Area Ona Kakanfo of Yorubaland. Successive Baale of Ogbomoso till 1870 acquired larger power at the expense of other competitors within the town (Akiele, 1895) NAL. To do this, the Baale exploited the disintegration of old Oyo Empire following the Afonja revolt and the Fulani conquest of Ilorin, to free himself from the tenuous political control of the Alaafin. The Baale now became the head of all the religious cults including Sango, Ogboni, Oro, and Agan cults mainly to sustain his power.

A new element was introduced into the town's politics from the 1820's with the arrival of a large population of displace persons and chiefs from neighboring town and villages as a result of Yoruba civil war i.e. from 1790s to 1830s. Ogbomoso became like Abekuta, a place where many found refuge. Unlike the latter however, it did not evolve a federal system of government that accommodated all interests in town. The Baale merely utilized the numerical strength of the refuges and their courage to reinforce the defense of the town while excluding them from political processes for the fear that they might seize power from him. In this policy the Baale received maximum support of his Ilu chiefs and the old antagonism seemed to disappear [Ayandele, 1966] for basic development.

Thereign of Ojo Aburumaku 1865-1869 marked the apogee of the Baale's arbitrariness. He had ruthlessly invoked all the latent powers vested on him to become a despot. Like Teyeje his father, he held the office of Aare-Onakakanfo to establish his authority not only in the town but also over neighboring Oyo towns and villages and he refuse to pay the customary homage to Alaafin. His rule had the plan of uniting the Ilu chiefs, the refugee chiefs and generality of people with a common cause to rid them of institutionalized tyranny. Because of his style of administration, most of his subjects nursed one grudge or the other against him. But he systematically pushed the turbulent among his soldiers and war captains out of town to against Ibadan in the Ijesha campaigns. But when his son, Otunla seized the throne in September 1869 in direct violation of the town's tradition forbidding father-son succession NAL, the climax was reached as chiefs and all their supporters teamed up with some Ogbomoso soldiers at Ilesha and obtained Ibadan's help to dethrone Otunla and installed Gbagun, the rightful candidate. This revolt has a great significance in Ogbomoso politic ever since. It entrenched the belief that the town's people and the chiefs could remove their rulers through an open revolt. BaaleGbagun ruled between 1870 to 1877 and became a citizen ruler and was coerced to accept certain administrative financial and judicial reforms that imposed some limitation upon his power [Ordinance, 1901 NAL].

The 1870 revolt sanctioned the constitutional power of Ogbomoso chiefs and citizens to open rebellion against an unpopular ruler. It also subordinated the town to Ibadan. Thereafter, Ogbomoso rulers lost their right to independent action on political and military matter in the period under review. Baalelaoye I [1877- 1901] had to accede to direct military demand from Ibadan during the Ekitiparapo and Kiriji wars which his predecessor, Gbagun [1870-1877] bowed to. The intervention of Aare Latoosa of Ibadan in the disagreement between Gbagun and a section of the Muslim community in the town brought peace to the land in 1876. Thus, this forged strong political links with Ibadan that later in the 1930s and 1940 proved irksome to Ogbomoso [Dickson, 1913] NAL.

Colonial rule and its impact on Ogbomoso Local Administration

Ogbomoso as one of the great Yoruba towns was not left out in the imposition of colonial rule at the end of the 19th century. The period was characterized by incessant internecine war which provides ample opportunities for the British Colonialist to interfere in the local administration of the Yoruba people. The inception of British colonial rule in Yorubaland in 1893 generally cause mixed feeling in the minds of many Ogbomoso people as to the real import of the new epoch. The Ekitiparapo and Kiriji wars that involved Ibadan and her allies including Ogbomoso on the one hand and the Ijesha and Ekiti on the other were over. Although Ilorin still remained belligerent and Ogbomoso felt relatively unsafe because of its nearness to that town there were assurances that Ilorin forces could not for long defy the British. Still Baale Laoye saw the British as intruder and a threat to his control of the town. In 1893, the new British resident in Ibadan, Captain R.L Bower, demanded that Baale Laoye should report all important administrative and judicial matters to him [Oyerinde, 1934].

In February 1895, a detachment of "Hausa" soldiers under Mr. Sarbine, a British officer, was stationed in the town to check Ilorin's incursions into Ogbomoso's territories. Baale Laoye came under the direct orders of the military officer and had to obey him on virtually all judicial and administrative matters. A clash between the two men was inevitable as the British had arrogated to themselves the right to interfere in the administration of the town, making such requirement as good for the people. The grudges between Baale Laoye and Mr. Sabine deteriorated to the extent that Baale Laoye refused to supply food to troops.

In July 1898, the acting Resident, Captain Erhardt, intervened to restore amicably the relationship between the two men promising to support Laoye's rule in every legitimate way. Finally on November 18, 1898, the troops were removed after the Royal Niger Company had conquered Bida and Ilorin. Baale Laoye was made responsible for the administration of the town. He however, swore obedience to the Resident, Captain Fuller in Ibadan (April, 1976).

To Ogbomoso people, the British present meant the enlargement of their liberties. Some of the Obas and Chiefs who migrated to Ogbomoso seized the opportunity and the prevailing peace to leave Ogbomoso and carved out new homestead, located not far from the town. An example was the Alajaawa who left in 1898. When Baale Laoye refused to permit him to leave, he claimed to be Alaafin's subject. The British Resident also supported him to leave, other refugee Obas followed Alajaawa's example. This created fear for Baale Laoye of losing control over his former subjects. The official delineation of the Ogbomoso district after 1901 ultimately removed the Baale's apprehensions (Lapage 1972, Oyerinde 1937).

The establishment of Baptist missionaries in the town created a room for new life; therefore the Baptist convert in the town also welcomes the British presence. The Reverend Charles E. Smith reported gleefully that the British held over the chiefs, threats of punishments or displacement in case of evil or injustice to the Baale. Therefore, some of the church elders openly defied the Baale order; while the Reverend Smith claimed final authority with the church (Oyerinde, 1937). This had a devastating effect on the authority of the Baale.

The 1901 Native Councils Ordinance formally set up the local government structure in Ogbomosoland under the colonial rule. The Ordinance recognized the Baale and his council, made up of Ilu chiefs, as the government of the town. As the president of the council, the Baale fixed meetings and decided on issues of the day, subject to the overriding power of the Ibadan Native Council and the Governor. In 1907, the Ogbomoso Council was formally constituted a native court but restricted its power by the Ibadan judicial council NAI.

The Native Authority Ordinance of 1917 however revolutionized the local government structure generally in Oyo province, with designated Native Authorities. Rulers were classified into three categories, and each was given sole powers of administration in their towns, districts or divisions. The Baale of Ogbomoso was a third class ruler and became by law an autocrat in his town and districts. He was subjected to the Baale of Ibadan, a second class ruler for efficient administration. The ordinance separated judicial from administration, while the Ilu chiefs served as judges of the native courts.

The establishment of the local government structure in Ogbomoso between 1901 and 1911 was therefore a gradual elimination from their previous positions of Baale's competitors for power. In 1901 the Ilu chiefs were recognized as part of the policy making organ of government, but by 1917 they were completely removed from this position because of colonial interest on Soun administrative system in general. The Baale was made the sole authority that determined all policies and decided on how to affect them on his subject. His traditional powers to appoint and dismiss any of his Ilu chiefs had received the British sanction in 1917.

The role of other chiefs in the town's administration paled into significance. The chiefs had become redundant since the end of Yoruba civil war and there was no policy to integrate them into the administration not until the first decade of the 20th century. For some time after 1917 two of his chiefs, the Aare Alaasa and Agoro sat on the native court as

judges. But in 1927, they were removed by Mr. Lapage, the district officer because they were not listed as judges in the warrant of the re-constituted court of 1922 (Dickson, 1938).

The reforms initiated by Governor Donald Cameron (1931-1935) into the system of Natives Authority had very important consequences in Ogbomoso. As it was in other parts of the Oyo and Ibadan divisions, they allowed a wider base for local politics than admitting representatives of the elite to achieve some socio-economic development for the towns and district. The changes were made relatively easier in the Ibadan division by the personality of the new British Resident, Mr. H.L Ward –Price who was the complete antithesis of his predecessor, Ross. Ward Price also encouraged the educated elite to form Progressive Unions through which public opinion were mobilized in the Ibadan division to influence the British to change their policy for making Alaafin supreme in the Ibadan and Oyo divisions. Ibadan division became administrative independent of the Alaafin in 1934.

In Ogbomoso the changes were introduced with the appointment of N.D. Oyerinde as a member of the Native Authority in 1931 and the revocation of the Baale's position as the sole Native Authority in 1934. He now had to rule with his Ilu chiefs. A primary object of the reforms as they affected Ogbomoso was to allow all rival groups within the town to participate in the local administration. Thus, the British hope to neutralize all opposition to the Native Authority, making it an effective organ for the maintenance of law and order within its area of jurisdiction. Secondly, the British saw the progressive Union as a vehicle for the expression of political, education and economic needs of different section of the town, therefore welcomed its inauguration. Notwithstanding, these hopes were dashed because there was no co-operation between the Baale and Ogbomoso Progressive Union (OPU). This had devastated effects on socio-economic progress to the town, with passage of time this was followed by discontent and acquiescence after the 1935 open confrontation between the duo from 1940 to 1951 (Agiri 1967).

The emergence of Baale Oyewumi as a new king in town was highly welcomed by the majority of people. He introduced new reforms to the extent that it did not affect his ultimate control on policy making. When his Ilu chiefs were intractable with Oyerinde's appointment to the native Authority Council, they encourage the Baale to honour him as Otun Baale. The OPU regarded this as a major task that will help the Baale to achieve efficiency in his administration.

It wanted, therefore, the Baale's control of the court, the integration of the other chiefs into the local administration and led to reduction of the Baale's overall powers in the town. Although, the Baale had an understanding of what socio-economic progress meant he wanted schools, post office, pipe-borne water and good roads in the town and he realized this with the co-operation of OPU. By 1948 all his aspiration for the town was achieved.

The British welcomed the OPU's suggestion in 1934 for the creation of a town and district Councils comprising sequentially all the chiefs in the town and district. But the OPU and the British have different aims. The British hoped that the new councils would stimulate self-expression among the chiefs, but more important, enable the Baale to control public opinion. The OPU on the other hand wished to unite opposition in the town and district against the Baale, to force him to co-operate with them. When the council was created in 1935, Baale Oyewumi realizing the intention of the OPU, set to create his own party among the chiefs. He allowed some of them to hear privately and illegally cases and litigations affecting people within their quarters.

Politically, the system of administration in Ogbomoso during the British colonial rule was modified because of the existence of different societies formed. Such associations included, Egbe Ilupeju (Ilupeju society) formed in 1939, Egbe Soun (Soun's society) formed to popularize the Baale's enlightened activities, The Egbe Ilu (society of the towns people) formed in 1994 and the Ogbomoso progressive Union (OPU) 1948 were all established to collaborate the Baale's activities in the town. After the February 1942 meeting, it became the usual practice that representative of all associations and societies meet to discuss town affairs. At such meeting, emphasis was placed upon the need for co-operation among all the associations and societies to achieve the progress of the town.

The national politics of the 1950s also influence the local administration in colonial Ogbomoso. From 1952, members of the parapo saw the changes in the struggle for policy determination in the local government in the western Region.

Conclusion

From the foregoing, it could be seen that local administration in colonial Ogbomoso shows a remarkable continuity with its pre-colonial past where the Bale and his Ilu chiefs were recognized as enforcers of the British order. The British pyramidal structure of local government was designed to make Baale autocratic because of the power arrogated to him as political hand of the town and member of native administration up to 1954. The foundation laid by the British in colonial Ogbomoso still remains in force.

In spite of the local government reform 1976, Soun still remains de-facto in traditional local administration of Ogbomoso as a whole.

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